
PUBLIC POLICY AS A BOOST OF SUSTAINABLE RURAL TOURISM

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Abstract

In this document, actions were proposed through a public policy so that the tourist activity would become the engine of development in the municipality of Teuchitlán, Jalisco, based on the involvement of society and an analysis of the existing tourist attractions of the same place. A mixed investigation was applied with statistical data, consultation of authors who have contributed to the subject or shared findings, statistical data from government sources, and also a correlational study. The results found through the opinions of community members share the idea that tourism is an essential part of their daily activity as a society and expressed that there is little investment in basic and tourist infrastructure in the municipality. In conclusion, there is a great possibility that this public policy will become a reality (endogenous development) since the community agrees that tourism is the central axis of development since it has attractions to become a tourist pole complementary to those offered by the state of Jalisco. At the same time, it is considered a good idea to apply this strategy to boost this activity in this county now that we are facing the impact of COVID-19 with its co-lateral impacts in health and economic issues.

Keywords: Public Policy, Local Development, Tourism, Sustainable Tourism, Endogenous Development

Introduction:

The social and economic development of Mexico has been distinguished by profound inequalities before and after the adaptation of the Neoliberal system in the '90s and the “world hydrocarbon crisis in the 80's” (Gómez-Carretero). marked development with deep disparities especially in rural areas such as lack of basic public services, low employment opportunities, exclusion of educational opportunities, and low per capita income.

The rural population presents serious socioeconomic lags, which are synthesized in their degree of marginalization. For the year 2000, it is estimated that 32.5 percent of rural localities have a very high degree of marginalization and 46.5 percent high, with a population of 4.1 and 12.4 million inhabitants, respectively (see Table 3 and 4), which means that two out of every three rural inhabitants live in localities with high or very high marginalization. (Hernández, 2003: 67)

Furthermore, this is evident with a comparison in the excessive economic and population concentration with the big capitals; in a marked political and cultural centralism, with its inequality in the allocation of fiscal resources and the almost null real exercise of the sovereignty of the municipality, are conditions that are maintained and deepened by the absence of a comprehensive municipal development plan that corrects the consequences spatial and income distribution, whose spontaneous tendency is to generate and deepen inequalities.

In traditional terms, it has been considered that inequalities in the municipality must be measurable and represented through socioeconomic and sustainability indicators. This is a need to fully understand all the problems that are generated in the municipality, and consequently part of the purpose of a diagnosis is the demonstration of existing inequalities.

It is important to note that the reality that the municipality is part of a region cannot be ignored as a fundamental condition of its plural diversity, but also of a particular recognition of a municipality and of what it is. It has in terms of natural and cultural resources.

In other words, in its most basic aspect, tourism development acquires meaning based on its nature as a tertiary activity and its requirements for a supply of services and consumption (demand); privileging the economic benefits produced by its management, to the detriment of the rest of its variables that make it a cultural, social and sustainable phenomenon.

The purpose of this work includes a broad approach where it is considered important not only the range of tourist services but also the quality of the service, not overlooking what the deprecation of natural resources (almost zero sustainable activity) and cultural elements mean. vital for the generation of opportunities, as well as the economic hardships of the community where tourist services are produced and offered. In such a way that the proposal through Public Policy (PP) understands that companies must assume leadership to re-unite business with society, where social problems are in the center, not in the periphery.

These characteristics are manifested by most of the municipalities far from the capitals of the states where federal support is minimal, which only covers current spending, this as a result of the commitment to development in the large cities of the country, according to expert. "Almost three out of four Mexicans lived in the countryside in 1900, only one remains in 2000" (Warman, 2004: 33).

Regional and local development is complex in Mexico since they depend to a greater degree on the federal entity to have the tools for social development, there is a coincidence with development principle from Boisier (2003)

Today development is understood as the achievement of a context, environment, momentum, situation, environment, or whatever it is called, that facilitates the empowerment of the human being to transform into a human person, in its dual dimension, biological and spiritual, capable, in this last condition, of knowing and loving. This means relocating the concept of development in a constructivist, subjective and intersubjective, evaluative or axiological framework, and, by the way, endogenous, that is, directly dependent on collective self-confidence in the ability to 'invent' resources, mobilize existing ones and act cooperatively and in solidarity, from the territory itself. (p. 131-161).

In this context, it is possible to make these ideas coincide with the concept of Social Capital, a principle that guides the work of theoreticians and public officials in our days.

Social capital is defined in this work as the set of norms of trust, values, attitudes, and networks that exist between social actors and social organizations present in tourist destinations, which facilitate cooperation and the achievement of common goals already set. (Vargas, 2002)

This association can have several dimensions of analysis, either at the individual level, between different social agents, or between social organizations in charge of regulating the rules of the

tourist activity game (institutions). On the other hand, it is possible to construct an analysis from the perspective of a collective dimension, social capital in this sense, is explained through the heritage and strength that society has.

This public policy proposal analyzes the municipality of Teuchitlán, Jalisco, which has natural and cultural attractions so that through this initiative it generates opportunities for local development under endogenous development. It is important to highlight that the reality that the municipality is part of a region cannot be ignored as a fundamental condition of its plural diversity, but also of a particular recognition of a municipality and what it has in terms of natural resources and culture.

Graph 1. Distribution of Economic Units. Teuchitlán, March 2019

Source: Own design with information from Economic Secretarial

But another axis that arises in this document is social capital where culture, society, private initiative, and the public sector are part of this proposal that tourism is an essential part of this PP (see graph 1). The central axis of this PP is society, which manifests itself, becomes involved, in a real and integral way within the territory, under the characteristics of rurality as stated by Carpio. (2000)

Consequently, rethinking a new Local Development for Rural Development is the challenge in these times of crossroads that forces a critical re-reading of theories, models, behaviors, scales, conception, and management of policies and even living together in rural spaces and the world. (p. 85)

An approach to the definition of public policy.

The implementation of public policies (PP) in Latin America have since the 70's and 80s. "As a discipline of knowledge and as a tool to reduce the economic crises that manifested themselves continuously in the '80s. with the discourse of autonomy in governance" (Aguilar, 2007). For PP to take place, a shared value must be combined between three sectors, which are the public, private initiative, and local society.

The current discourse of the PP traces it back to epistemic communities, according to this approach it refers to. "A group of people or entities that share a certain perception about public problems and try to promote a set of analyzes and proposals to promote a policy or a normative change". (Subirats, 1989), towards this approach it refers to causing innovation in political decisions where society plays an important role in their application and above all that review actors are currently emerging from the same.

Sustainable view

In the last decade the speech of sustainable development has been an important issue in Mexico since the academy thru the politicians have been taken into account to make aware the importance of this topic, but one sector, the industry, has been struggling to settle in their goals, they consider that the monetary income is the most important rather than the society and the environment.

There have been lots of international conventions to make conscious and establish agreements to reduce the negative impacts to the environment, one of them is the Brundtland Report (1987), but results have not been enough to let the right conditions for future generations as the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987) describes sustainable development. "Development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs."

Graph 1. Dimension of sustainable development

Source: <http://www.un.org/en/sustainability/>

Location background.

Starting from the perspective of economic development, in which most of the authors who study local performance based on economic behavior, leaving social development in the background away from the analysis of the social dimension from where it is possible to study the roles of local agents capable of envisioning an economic and social model in which communities develop their development proposals, that is, endogenous development. The theory of local development establishes as a condition for integral development that decisions arise from the community agents themselves; that is, leadership is born in the community, and decisions to come from within the community itself. In this sense, this model seeks the satisfaction of basic needs, community participation, and environmental conservation: sustainable development, that is, there are real opportunities where community members are the central axis of the Public politics.

From this perspective, endogenous development has its goal in the community so that development transcends upwards, towards the economy of the municipality with benefits to the members of the Teuchitlán community, and under this perspective, it is possible to reduce the negative indicators that are observed In the community as it is development, a change is seen in the decrease of emigration to large cities and especially to the United States of America.

Through the years under the neoliberal economic model, businessmen seek to obtain greater benefits regardless of the negative effect on human resources that settle in a specific location, with long working hours, in many cases with zero social security benefits and benefits for be hired through the phenomenon of "outsourcing" trying to modify the mentality of the business sector with a new mentality focused on shared development.

Methods & Materials:

In order to adopt a comprehensive approach that allows a better understanding of the study, it is important to observe the multiplicity of variables at stake and their diverse nature (economic, technological, demographic, social, cultural, legal, etc.). Therefore, it is necessary to identify all the determining factors of PP dynamics, both internal and external, and allow:

- Have a series of representation instruments to identify the key factors and determine the relevant indicators or variables according to the available information.
- Establish existing interdependencies distinguished direct and indirect chance links.
- Define the factors that may be risk or opportunity, in the short, medium and long term.

Research method:

This analysis is based on the exploratory study, since the content will allow us to become familiar with the integration of the main actors.

- Type of study: Mixed: it is necessary to make comparisons on past and current aspects, to know the economic and demographic advances that are present, as well as to take into account the society that becomes involved so as not to generate additional damage to the change.

A correlational study will also be applied that measure two or more variables (Tourism-sustainable development-social capital) to verify whether or not they are related in the same subject (society) and then the correlation (public policy) is analyzed. It is important to point out in most cases, the measurements in the variables to be correlated come from the same subjects. (Campos / Sosa 2011).

Subjects and objects of study

The rethinking of the public administration and private initiative to generate projects that benefit the community, in this case tourism as a generator of opportunities.

The subjects or elements to be investigated are the members of the community.

Results and Discussion:

According to The United Nations Development Program (UNDP, 2001).

Considers that human development is a process through which citizens expand their capacities in such a way that it allows them to extend their lives, improve their knowledge and have the necessary financial resources to carry out a dignified life, this concept then, sees the human being as a fundamental piece in the development of countries and has launched proposals to challenge based on this approach.

Given this, the importance of the participation of the local population in making decisions is considered in the face of the opportunity that another activity (tourist activity) becomes opportunities to be analyzed from different aspects: tourist, social, economic and environmental; However, after this study carried out for academic purposes - assuming the importance of the implementation of this PP in the Municipality of Teuchitlán, Jalisco, it is noted that one of the main aspects to be rescued is the position of the majority of the population towards the tourism sector, which perceives it as an opportunity to generate main or complementary economic benefits to the activities of the primary sector carried out in the community.

It is very important to consider the local community (endogenous development) as an agent of change, since this type of rural spaces, their culture, traditions and habits are deeply rooted and the intention of this study is that the community members themselves do hers this tourism project (empowering) as a way to improve their economic activity, whether main or complementary, and thus improve their integral living conditions.

Development, creativity and entrepreneurial capacity therefore go hand in hand to achieve whatever objective is set. The free exercise of capacities by citizens is what allows a constant transformation to be generated both in society itself and in the economy. Therefore, it is understood that man is the center in which the economy moves and transforms and the activities that he carries out will always be seen as a means to achieve his objectives, never as an end for their realization.

In this case, taking into account the endogenous development, Teuchitlán can take part of its three types. In the first instance, generate and / or properly use an inventory of all its attractions, whether natural or cultural generators of identity, especially the involvement of its population, the attitude to be participatory, purposeful and generators of initiatives; in conjunction with

(academic) specialists in the area and the government of the municipality through a sustainable management of resources.

The creative process will therefore be applied based on the resources, potential and factors of the territory such as culture, natural and cultural attractions. However, if it is intended to transfer to this approach as a sustainable vision where it only occurs in a welfare way, therefore it does not allow citizens to collaborate with its development.

Teuchitlán at this point and based on the territorial analysis and the study through the applied survey, has great potential since it has various natural attractions such as the La Vega dam, the Teuchitlán River, the Tequila volcano, the La Saucedá forest area. and cultural ones such as Los Guachimontones, the museum house of culture, its main square, the church of the Lord of the Ascension and the Hacienda Labor de Rivera to mention a few adding that not all of them are used and encouraged to do recreational activities; But on the other hand, we have that the majority of the economically active population is engaged in commercial or labor activities and only thirty percent of these people obtain an economic benefit derived from tourism, therefore the population does have an entrepreneurial vision, since the The town has vast commercial premises of various branches, so the problem is in obtaining sources of financing and government support so that sources of employment are generated through tourism. It is therefore important to make an analysis of which companies would need to be developed so that the activity can perform with more vigor.

It is intended to give continuity to this project with a sustainable development approach, since this instrument was of great help and gives us a guideline to carry out strategies on the project's objectives, such as the first of endogenous development, shared value, heritage conservation.

Given the nature that most municipalities in Mexico are partially forgotten by the neoliberal economic policy implemented in the early 90's that gives greater importance to the generation of wealth regardless of the negative impact on society and profound effects on the environment; the Municipality of Teuchitlán, Jalisco is in the same situation.

Nowadays, that we are facing health and economic problems by COVID 19 we should take these as opportunity to propose new PP to booster local communities making tourism as a development lever because during 2008 and 2009, we experienced similar economic

contraction especially in tourism industry and the national tourism made this sector stronger again.

Any form of tourism which highlights the rural life, art, culture, heritage, at rural sites, thereby supporting the Hosts (Local) community socially, economically as well as enabling interaction among the Guests (tourists) and the Hosts (Locals) for more experience & enrichment can be called as rural tourism. This type of tourism takes place in rural sites of Darjeeling Hills and the concept of homestay is developing in rural areas empowering the rural economy of the region. Rural tourism's greatest potential benefit is its ability to generate money, which can translate into numerous positive economic opportunities for locals and their communities. For locals the first benefit of tourism development is jobs within the tourism sectors and outside of it. Tourism development means more income and profits for tourists related business. The economic multiplier model suggests that if local income from tourist expenditures is spent within local area, an increase in local income & jobs will follow.

Conclusion:

Home stay or tea tourism is two of the options most popular among the tourist in rural areas in Darjeeling hills. The stay is with very basic facilities and creates less impact environmentally. A home stay concept preferred by most of the tourist is fast catching up locally and internationally. Home stay is arranged and run by villagers and it includes staying in Tea Gardens or Tea Estate or villages or a whole village set up made especially for the guest. Birding, short trails, angling are part of the stay and are not spoken or written separately, it is part of the concept. The stay is simple with basic infrastructure and is about bringing one closer to local cultures and environment. Local guide from the destination will help guest with their cultures and ways of life far better and earn a much needed income. Interaction with travelers and the knowledge that they are visiting for the richness in the culture brings in a sense of pride amongst the local people and also brings in supplementary sources of income hence it makes economic sense to the villagers as well. The popularity is fast catching up and many of the rural places in this region are setting up home stay facilities with some form of adventure for the tourist. There are number of such home stay facilities in the region. The visit helps the economy, buying local products, buying art materials and using local villagers as guide or help.

Rural tourism will emerge as an important instrument for sustainable human development including poverty alleviation, employment generation, environmental regeneration and development of remote areas and advancement of women and other weaker

section of the society. If a proper planning is done rural tourism, could bring lots of benefit to the society. It could be a sustainable revenue-generating project for the rural people in this region. It can help inflow to resources from urban to the rural economy. It can also prevent migration of rural people to urban. Both short term and long term planning, implementing and monitoring are vital in avoiding damage to rural areas also. To conclude, the tourism potential in rural parts, if properly planned can become a source of further income and regional development for the rural livelihoods.

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